

AN EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE BLAST RESISTANCE OF SANDWICH COMPOSITES WITH A STEPWISE GRADED CORE

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SUMMARY

Two types of sandwich panels, having identical core materials, but different core layer arrangement with respect to the density, were subjected to shock wave loading using a shock tube apparatus. The results indicated that a sandwich panel with a monotonously increasing core layer density outperformed that with a discontinuous core layer density.

Keywords: Sandwich Structure, Discretely Layered Core, Shock Wave Loading, Dynamic Failure, High Speed Imaging

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures have been used as a blast mitigation strategy in the naval and aerospace industries, due to their properties in dispersing the mechanical impulse and protecting the structures located behind it [1-3]. The core materials play a crucial role in the blast resistance of sandwich structures. Stepwise graded materials, where the material properties vary gradually or layer by layer within the material itself, were utilized as a novel core material in sandwich composites in recent years. Since these types of cores can be designed and controlled, they show great potential to be an effective core material for absorbing and dispersing the blast energy and improving the overall blast resistance of sandwich structures.

The dynamic behaviors of sandwich composites with different core materials under blast loading have been widely studied [1-9]. However, the properties of sandwich composites with a stepwise graded core material under blast loading have not been studied. Limited low-velocity impact results of sandwich composites with stepwise structures are available. The numerical investigation by Apetre et al. [10] has shown that a reasonable core design can effectively reduce the shear forces and strains within the structures. Consequently, they can mitigate or completely prevent impact damage on sandwich composites. Li et al. [11] found that the choice of gradation has a great significance on the impact response of layered and graded metal-ceramic structures and the particular design can exhibit better energy dissipation properties.

The present study focuses on the mechanisms of deformation and dynamic failure of sandwich composites with stepwise graded foam cores under shock wave loading. Two types of sandwich composites with identical core materials but different core layer

arrangements were subjected to shock wave loading generated by a shock tube. The shock pressure profiles and real time deformation images were carefully analyzed to reveal the failure mechanisms of these two sandwich composites and their relative performances were also compared.

MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN

The skin materials utilized in this study were E-Glass Vinyl Ester (EVE) composites comprised of 18oz. E-glass fiber and a vinyl-ester matrix. The plain weave woven roving E-glass fibers of the skin material were placed in a quasi-isotropic layout [0/45/90/-45]_s.

The core materials were Corecell™ A series styrene foams, which were manufactured by Gurit SP Technologies. The three types of Corecell™ A series foam were A300, A500 and A800 with density 58.5, 92 and 150 kg/ m³ respectively. The cell structures for the three foams are very similar with the only difference arising in the cell wall thickness and node sizes, which accounts for the different foam densities.

Figure 1 Specimen configuration and loading direction

The sandwich panels were 102 mm (4 in) wide, 254 mm (10 in) long with front and back skins approx 5 mm (.2 in) thick. For the core, there were three layers, with each layer 12.7 mm (.5 in) thick respectively. The total thickness was 48 mm (1.9 in). Fig. 1 shows the two core layer configurations and the shock wave loading direction. Configuration 1 consisted of a core gradation of A300/A500/ A800 (low / middle / high density), and configuration 2 consisted of a core gradation of A500/A300/A800 (middle / low / high density). The average areal density of the samples was 19.02 kg/m².

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND PROCEDURE

The shock tube apparatus was utilized to obtain the controlled shock wave loading. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2a. A panel specimen was placed in front of muzzle end in the support fixtures. A high speed digital camera, IMACON 200, was used to capture the real time side view deformation images of the specimen. Fig. 2b gives the

detailed dimensions and locations of the muzzle, specimen, supports and the pressure transducers (PCB102A). The inner diameter of the final muzzle is 0.0762 m (3 in). The transducers are mounted at the end of the muzzle section to measure the incident pressure and the reflected pressure during the experiment. The distance between the two transducers is 0.16m and the distance between the second transducer and the end of the muzzle is ~0.02m. The support fixtures ensure simply supported boundary conditions with a 0.1524 m (6 in) span and the support lines are parallel to the wide side of the panel.

Figure 2 Experimental setup and the detail of muzzle of the shock tube

In the present study, a shock wave, with an incident overpressure of approximately 1 MPa and a velocity of approximately 1030 m/s, was generated and loaded on the panels. For each configuration, at least three samples were tested. With an interframe time of 70 μ s and an exposure time of 700 ns, approximately 14 high speed image frames could be obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Real Time Deformation

The real time deformation images of configuration 1 (A300/A500/A800) and configuration 2 (A500/A300/ A800) are shown in fig.3 and fig. 4 respectively. The shock wave propagates from the right side of the image to the left side.

For configuration 1, as shown in fig. 3, the first core layer subjected to the shock wave is A300 and the core gradation is from the foam of least density and lowest strength to the foam of highest density. In this case, the indentation failure of the front skin at $t = 70 \mu$ s means that A300 foam layer was in failure at that time. After indentation of the front skin began, the panel showed two combined deformation mechanisms: bending and first layer compression. Since foam materials have long compression stress plateau, the compression of the first layer (A300) kept the stress level in the panel at a low level. Therefore, this core compression mechanism weakened the shock wave loading by the time it reached the back skin. The double-winged deformation shape showed that the sandwich structure was under shear mode. The onset of core failure, where core

cracking began, was observed at $t = 280 \mu\text{s}$ and the initial separation / delamination of the front skin from the core was observed at $t = 770 \mu\text{s}$. Complete core collapse and failure was not observed for this configuration.

Fig. 3 Real Time Observation of A300/A500/A800 Under Shock Loading

In configuration 2, as shown in fig. 4, A500 is the first core layer subjected to the shock wave and the core gradation begins with the foam of middle density and middle strength, next the foam of least density and lowest strength, and then the highest density and highest strength foam. In this case, the beginning of the front skin indentation is not very clear. The global bending of the panel recovered this initial indentation. There is no obvious core compression before $t = 490 \mu\text{s}$. Even after $t = 490 \mu\text{s}$, the compression of the middle layer (A300 foam) was only visible where the supports were located and there was still no obvious core compression in the middle of the panel where the loading was applied. This means that compression was due to the large shear stress under large bending deflection. The double-winged deformation shape also showed that the sandwich structure was under shear mode. The onset of core failure, where core cracking began, can be seen at $t = 140 \mu\text{s}$ and the onset of complete collapse of the core initiates at $t = 490 \mu\text{s}$, where the core cracking had traveled completely through the core, resulting catastrophic core failure.

Fig. 4 Real Time Observation of A500/A300/A800 Under Shock Loading

Fig. 5 Deflection of A300/A500/A800

Fig. 6 Deflection of A500/A300/A800

The mid-point deflections of the front face (front skin), interface 1 (between first and second core layer), interface 2 (between second and third core layer), and back face (back skin) for configuration 1 and configuration 2 are plotted in fig. 5 and fig. 6. For configuration 1 (A300/A500/A800), the front face deflects to ~33 mm at ~t = 840μs,

which is approximately 25% more than the other three constituents. This means only the first layer A300 foam between the front face (skin) and interface 1 was in compression and the compression strain was closed to 90%. On the contrary, all of the constituents of configuration 2 (A500/A300/A800) deflected in the same manner. This shows almost no obvious compression in the mid-point area, even though the core foams of configuration 1 and configuration 2 were identical.

The major failure mechanism in configuration 2 was progressive shear damage of the core. Many cracks and delaminations were visible in the cores and interfaces which led to panel bending followed by a rapid crushing of the core and catastrophic failure of the sandwich structure. Contrary to the case of configuration 2, the major failure mechanism in configuration 1 was core compression. With identical core materials and the same level shock wave loading, configuration 1 had no complete core collapse while configuration 2 disintegrated into pieces. This indicates that the core layer arrangement can improve the overall performance of the sandwich structures subjected to shock wave loading.

Post Mortem Images

Fig. 7 Post mortem images of sandwich panels

The damage patterns of the sandwich panels after the shock event occurred were visually examined and recorded using a high resolution digital camera and are shown in Fig.7. For configuration 1, there were two main cracks visible and they were located between the support positions and the positions where the shock wave loading was applied. Delamination was visible between the front skin and the foam core, as well as the back skin and the foam core. Obvious core compression was seen in the first layer (A300) and second layer (A500). Note that the residual compression strain of A300 layer in the mid-point area is about 40%, which means the compression strain recovered 50% after the shock wave loading occurred. This shows the good performance of the Corecell™ A series foam as a core material. Unlike the damage visible in configuration 1, configuration 2 suffered catastrophic damage. The core of the sandwich disintegrated and the front skin (blast side) of the sandwich fractured into two pieces at

the midsection. The back skin showed an extensive amount of fiber delamination in the central region as well. Note that the permanent back face deflection of configuration 1 is much larger than that of configuration 2. This means configuration 1 is more flexible than configuration 2.

An interesting phenomenon was visible in the first core layer (A500) of configuration 2 in the real time deformation image. Here a flat segment was discovered, indicating the stress in that segment was released. The cracks observed on both sides of the flat segment do not resemble those caused by the bending shear stresses near the supports. The detailed macroscopic images of the local cracks and delamination surfaces show that the delamination surfaces exhibit similar material granules as those observed in a pure tension test.

Fig. 8 The failure details in configuration 2 (A500/A300/A800)

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Two types of sandwich panels with identical foam core materials but different core layer arrangements were subjected to shock wave loading by a shock tube. The two configurations were arranged according to the density of the respective foam; configuration 1 (A300/A500/A800) consisted of low / middle / high density foams and configuration 2 (A500/A300/A800) consisted of middle / low / high density foams. For configuration 1, large compression was visible in the lowest density foam core layer (A300). This configuration reduces the dynamic pressures seen on the back face sheet, and thus limits the total amount of damage imparted on the specimen. For configuration 2, compression in the core was limited and the specimen showed a heavy amount of damage. Overall performance of configuration 1 outperformed configuration 2.

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